

ASSESSMENT OF QUALITY OF LIFE IN COMBINED POST-BURN CICATRICIAL STRICTURES OF THE PHARYNX, ESOPHAGUS, AND STOMACH

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis of quality of life in 68 patients who underwent pharyngocoloplasty for combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach. The authors performed a statistical comparative analysis of the results of patients’ subjective self-assessment and clinical symptoms using the Visual Rating Scale (VRS), the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), the Spielberger State–Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), and the SF-36 Health Survey over the course of the study.*

Keywords: *pharyngocoloplasty; combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the esophagus; quality of life assessment.*

Introduction

Quality of life (QoL) is defined as a “characteristic of a person’s physical, psychological, emotional, and social functioning based on their subjective perception” [2]. As dissatisfaction with the conditions of modern life increases, the study of quality of life—initially rejected in the contemporary industrial world due to its perceived vagueness and lack of substantive content—now requires active investigation, without which any research aimed at meeting human needs is doomed to failure [3]. The principal surgical components of QoL in such patients are rightly considered to be the degree of dysphagia in relation to the severity of the maximal stricture, as well as the rate of food passage through the gastrointestinal tract and the pace of restoration of normal body weight [9].

The best quality of life has been observed in patients after surgical procedures using the whole stomach to create an artificial esophagus; isoperistaltic small-intestinal reconstruction ranks second; an artificial esophagus constructed from the colon in an antiperistaltic position demonstrated satisfactory results; while the most favorable outcomes were achieved with local reconstructive procedures when the native esophagus was preserved [4]. Self-assessment of one’s own condition clearly reflects the level of quality of life, although it varies widely among individuals [6, 7].

Aim of the study. To assess the quality of life of patients in terms of the immediate and long-term effectiveness of standard and newly developed surgical methods for combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach.

Materials and methods. In accordance with the study design, a comparative analysis of the dynamics of quality of life was conducted in 68 patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach, aged 4–85 years (mean age 34.43 ± 0.66 years). All patients underwent inpatient examination and treatment in the Department of Esophageal and Gastric Surgery of the State Institution “Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical

Center of Surgery named after Academician V. Vakhidov” during the period from 2000 to 2023. Quality of life was assessed at the following time points: within the first 24 hours after hospital admission, after completion of treatment, and at 6 months, 1 year, 2 years, and 3 years following treatment.

The patients were divided into two groups: the main group (MG) consisted of 39 patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach who underwent surgery using the method developed by the authors for forming a pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction (invention patent IAP No. 05835 “Method for forming a pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass coloplasty”); the comparison group (CG) included 29 patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach who underwent surgical correction of cicatricial narrowing of the pharynx and esophagus by creating an anastomosis with an oblique-transverse incision of the esophagus.

A statistical comparative analysis was performed to evaluate the results of patients’ subjective self-assessment and clinical symptoms using the Visual Rating Scale (VRS), the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), the Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), and the SF-36 Health Survey over the course of the study.

Results and discussion. Comparative analysis of the dynamics of overall condition scores according to the VRS demonstrated a statistically significant intergroup difference as early as 6 months after surgical correction of combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach, which persisted throughout the entire period of dynamic follow-up (Table 1).

Table 1. Dynamics of subjective assessment of overall condition according to the VRS in patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach ($M \pm m$).

Follow-up period	MG (n = 39)	CG (n = 29)	p-value
At admission	8.82 ± 0.79	8.91 ± 0.84	0.938029
At discharge	5.36 ± 0.64*	5.89 ± 0.82*	0.612113
After 6 months	3.54 ± 0.35*	4.76 ± 0.45*	0.036111
After 1 year	2.44 ± 0.42*	4.12 ± 0.59*	0.023507
After 2 years	2.28 ± 0.48*	3.94 ± 0.54*	0.024813
After 3 years	2.14 ± 0.41*	3.42 ± 0.47*	0.044174

* Difference compared with the baseline value is statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

A similar pattern was observed for clinical symptomatology, particularly dysphagia, the dynamics of which also demonstrated a statistically significant intergroup difference beginning at 6 months and persisting until the end of the follow-up period.

Table 2. Dynamics of subjective assessment of dysphagia according to the Visual Rating Scale (VRS) in patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach ($M \pm m$).

Follow-up period	MG (n = 39)	CG (n = 29)	p-value
At admission	8.47 ± 0.94	8.51 ± 0.89	0.975444
At discharge	6.44 ± 0.87	7.09 ± 0.91	0.607400
After 6 months	3.17 ± 0.49*	4.51 ± 0.42*	0.041822
After 1 year	2.51 ± 0.47*	3.92 ± 0.49*	0.041789
After 2 years	2.27 ± 0.41*	3.41 ± 0.37*	0.042993

After 3 years	$2.09 \pm 0.38^*$	$3.19 \pm 0.39^*$	0.047494
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* Difference compared with the baseline value is statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

In addition, it should be noted that the onset of statistically significant differences in overall condition scores relative to baseline was comparable between both groups and was already observed at the time of hospital discharge. In contrast, statistically significant differences in dysphagia scores relative to baseline in both study groups emerged only 6 months after discharge from the hospital. Thus, based on the VRS data, we concluded that the method of forming a pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction developed by the authors demonstrates greater subjective effectiveness compared with the conventionally used surgical technique (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the indicators assessed by the Visual Rating Scale (VRS) in patients.

A comparative evaluation of patients in the study groups was also performed with regard to the dynamics of psychological status using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) (Table 6.6). Subclinical anxiety was observed in 32 (82.05%) patients in the main group (MG), while 7 (17.95%) patients had clinically significant anxiety; in the comparison group (CG), these proportions were 26 (89.66%) and 3 (10.34%) patients, respectively, with no statistically significant intergroup difference ($p = 0.597$). According to the depression subscale of the HADS, clinically significant depression was identified in 27 (69.23%) patients in the MG and subclinical depression in 12 (30.77%) patients, whereas in the CG, 23 (79.31%) patients had clinically significant depression and 6 (20.69%) had subclinical depression; no statistically significant intergroup difference was observed ($p = 0.514$).

Thus, the baseline levels of the study groups on the HADS subscales were comparable, with depression being more pronounced; in the majority of patients, it was clinically expressed, although not at the maximum possible severity. At the time of hospital discharge, patients in both groups were characterized by subclinical levels of anxiety and depression according to the HADS. Normalization of anxiety on the HADS anxiety subscale occurred as early as 6 months after surgery, whereas a statistically significantly better psychological state in the main group was observed at 2 years postoperatively; similarly, statistically significant intergroup differences were identified at 2 years of follow-up.

Table 3. Dynamics of scores on the HADS subscales in patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach ($M \pm m$)

HADS – Anxiety			
Follow-up period	MG (n = 39)	CG (n = 29)	p-value
At admission	10.85 ± 1.03	10.87 ± 1.08	0.846534
At discharge	7.22 ± 0.71*	7.91 ± 0.82*	0.526918
After 6 months	6.14 ± 0.45*	7.23 ± 0.54*	0.125836
After 1 year	6.02 ± 0.32*	6.98 ± 0.35*	0.047052
After 2 years	5.64 ± 0.38*	6.67 ± 0.34*	0.047509
After 3 years	5.13 ± 0.32*	6.46 ± 0.38*	0.009389

HADS – Depression			
Follow-up period	MG (n = 39)	CG (n = 29)	p-value
At admission	10.98 ± 1.07	11.37 ± 1.16	0.805588
At discharge	7.82 ± 0.99*	8.56 ± 1.08	0.615206
After 6 months	6.17 ± 0.47*	7.48 ± 0.56*	0.077814
After 1 year	6.12 ± 0.33*	7.18 ± 0.41*	0.048149
After 2 years	5.64 ± 0.36*	6.73 ± 0.40*	0.046928
After 3 years	5.35 ± 0.34*	6.40 ± 0.39*	0.046517

* Difference compared with baseline is statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Figure 2. Dynamics of HADS scale indicators in patients of both groups.

According to the HADS depression subscale, normalization of patients' condition in the main group (MG) was observed at 6 months, whereas in the comparison group (CG) it occurred only after 2 years; moreover, intergroup comparison revealed a statistically significant difference after 1 year of follow-up. This finding allows us to conclude that the method of forming a pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction developed by the authors demonstrates greater subjective psychological effectiveness compared with the formation of an anastomosis using an oblique-transverse incision of the esophagus.

When performing a comparative analysis of the dynamics of state and trait anxiety using the Spielberger State–Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI), a statistically significant intergroup difference on the state anxiety subscale was identified only at the 3-year follow-up, indicating comparable psychological responses to their condition in patients of both groups (Table 4).

Table 4. Dynamics of STAI scores in patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach ($M \pm m$)

STAI – State anxiety

Follow-up period	MG (n = 39)	CG (n = 29)	p-value
At admission	58.45 ± 5.59	62.43 ± 5.61	0.616979
At discharge	44.58 ± 3.71*	49.82 ± 4.52	0.373510
After 6 months	32.17 ± 3.47*	34.26 ± 3.51*	0.673367
After 1 year	29.16 ± 2.42*	32.28 ± 2.48*	0.371225
After 2 years	24.14 ± 2.36*	29.31 ± 2.43*	0.131801
After 3 years	21.11 ± 2.31*	27.76 ± 2.35*	0.047716

STAI – Trait anxiety

Follow-up period	MG (n = 39)	CG (n = 29)	p-value
At admission	56.74 ± 4.78	58.69 ± 4.82	0.708402
At discharge	40.22 ± 3.21*	42.67 ± 3.32*	0.597556
After 6 months	33.39 ± 2.89*	35.51 ± 2.98*	0.611295
After 1 year	24.12 ± 2.41*	28.75 ± 2.82*	0.216457
After 2 years	22.03 ± 2.17*	26.44 ± 2.24*	0.162123
After 3 years	22.02 ± 2.21*	25.85 ± 2.22*	0.225870

* Difference compared with the level at admission is statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

Figure 3. Dynamics of STAI test indicators in patients of both groups.

We observed a statistically significant reduction in state anxiety according to the STAI test in the main group (MG) already at the time of discharge, whereas in the comparison group (CG) this reduction was noted only 6 months after surgical correction. At the same time, trait anxiety according to the STAI test showed statistically significant changes compared with baseline as early as discharge in both groups; however, no statistically significant intergroup differences for this scale were achieved throughout the entire follow-up period.

In addition, a dynamic comparative analysis of quality of life (QoL) was performed using the general health questionnaire SF-36. Mean scores were calculated and compared between groups, as well as with baseline values, for each individual scale of the questionnaire and for the overall mean score at each time point (Table 5).

Analysis of the SF-36 results in patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach in both subgroups, compared with general population norms, revealed a marked, nearly fourfold reduction in quality of life on the Physical Functioning (PF) scale. This finding is undoubtedly associated with the underlying pathology, which leads to a pronounced limitation of daily physical activity not attributable to general health status, and consequently also affects Role Physical functioning (RP). The decrease in quality of life with respect to the Bodily Pain (BP) parameter reflects the predominance of subjective pain sensations in patients of the comparison group, although without a statistically significant difference from the main group in terms of limitations of daily activities.

The subjective assessment of general health (GH) at admission was also reduced by nearly fourfold compared with population norms in both study groups, with a slightly worse trend observed in the main group. Quality of life according to the Vitality (VT) scale was found to be almost twofold lower than population norms, which is quite logical given the presence of developing alimentary disorders that inevitably affect vitality, energy, and vigor in patients of both groups.

Table 5. Dynamics of SF-36 questionnaire scores in patients of the study groups ($M \pm m$)

Indicator	Before treatment	At discharge	After 6 months	After 1 year	After 2 years	After 3 years
MG (n = 39)						
PF	16,44±4,68	35,79±5,53#	47,41±6,81#	51,85±7,39#	56,12±7,51#	58,41±7,43#
RP	15,32±4,69	34,81±5,32#	47,22±6,88#	51,36±7,37#	56,18±7,27#	59,14±7,39#
BP	14,41±3,47	28,34±6,47#	45,23±6,66#	52,25±6,82#	54,18±7,23#	57,86±7,57#
GH	16,37±2,59	32,44±6,62#	46,92±6,75#	52,16±7,28#	55,46±7,27#	58,59±7,18#
VT	23,19±4,87	37,19±6,29#	45,68±6,17#	54,25±7,01#	57,14±7,07#	61,65±7,29#
SF	12,46±3,19	27,55±6,45	46,27±6,09#	53,23±6,26#	58,89±6,42#	62,17±6,35#
RE	14,28±3,65	32,47±5,44#	48,99±5,92#	55,11±6,29#	59,42±6,19#	62,24±6,41#
MH	19,56±3,81	30,12±6,52#	46,61±5,46#	54,18±6,69#	58,17±6,52#	61,91±6,59#
Mean score	16,50±3,12	34,46±6,04#	46,04±6,33#	53,17±7,14#	56,20±7,09#	58,56±7,18#
Mean increase [§]	-	17,96±3,04	29,54±3,07	36,67±3,86*	39,72±3,94*	42,06±3,79*
CG (n = 29)						
	Before treatment	At discharge	After 6 months	After 1 year	After 2 years	After 3 years
PF	15,26±5,44	33,24±5,72#	40,91±8,69#	43,22±7,27#	45,32±7,19#	48,21±7,15#
RP	15,03±5,10	33,89±5,36#	41,12±7,94#	44,41±7,12#	47,11±7,10#	49,81±7,16#
BP	16,39±3,07	26,78±5,99#	41,63±7,78#	46,21±7,14#	49,41±6,98#	52,22±7,04#
GH	15,97±3,09	30,87±6,58#	41,38±7,74#	46,27±7,10#	49,21±7,09#	52,24±7,11#
VT	23,41±4,88	36,29±6,44#	40,21±6,94#	43,21±7,16#	45,32±7,21#	48,81±7,21#
SF	12,28±4,04	20,09±5,94#	41,21±6,96#	45,24±7,11#	47,46±7,08#	50,04±7,09#
RE	13,98±3,31	30,86±5,69#	39,21±6,06#	43,27±7,14#	45,67±7,04#	49,14±7,17#
MH	19,39±3,92	30,03±6,68#	37,41±6,61#	42,23±7,17#	45,03±7,03#	48,29±7,08#
Mean score	16,46±4,97	30,26±6,12#	40,39±7,14#	44,26±7,19#	46,82±7,09#	49,85±7,08#
Mean increase [§]	-	13,79±1,16	23,92±2,15	27,79±2,18	30,35±2,11	33,38±2,09

Note: PF – Physical Functioning, RP – Role Physical Functioning, BP – Bodily Pain, GH –

General Health, VT – Vitality, SF – Social Functioning, RE – Role Emotional Functioning, MH – Mental Health.

* Difference is statistically significant compared with the corresponding indicator of the parallel group at $p \leq 0.05$.

\$ Compared with the baseline level.

Difference is statistically significant compared with the pre-treatment value within the same group at $p \leq 0.05$.

Social Functioning (SF) reflects the degree of socialization of the patients; a decrease in this subscale was observed to be 4.5-fold in the main group and fivefold in the comparison group relative to population norms, indicating a reduction in the frequency and quality of relationships with friends, relatives, colleagues, and surrounding individuals. Low scores on the Role Emotional (RE) scale indicate a significant impact of depressed emotional status on daily life activities; in both groups, the mean score on this scale was approximately fourfold lower than population norms.

The subjective assessment of Mental Health (MH), which reflects mood, happiness, calmness, and emotional well-being, showed that at admission patients in the main group demonstrated a 2.9-fold reduction compared with population norms, whereas in the comparison group the reduction was 3.1-fold. It should be noted, however, that no statistically significant differences between the groups were observed on the SF-36 scales at admission ($p \geq 0.05$), although the greatest difference was recorded for the Vitality (VT) parameter, with smaller differences observed for Bodily Pain (BP) and Mental Health (MH).

We found no statistically significant differences from baseline across all SF-36 questionnaire scales in either group from the time of hospital discharge through the end of the follow-up period. It should also be noted that no statistically significant intergroup differences were observed for any of the SF-36 indicators at any time point during dynamic follow-up. Based on the obtained quality-of-life (QoL) results, it can be concluded that the emotional and physical components of patients' functioning are subjectively similar for both surgical techniques; that is, when surgical intervention is performed adequately and competently, the specific method used has little impact on patients' long-term outcomes.

However, comparative intergroup analysis of the increase in the mean SF-36 score relative to baseline revealed a statistically significant difference in favor of the main group (MG) at 1 year after surgical correction ($p = 0.049336$). A similar pattern was observed at 2 years after surgery ($p = 0.039937$) and at 3 years of follow-up ($p = 0.049075$). Nevertheless, a clear and persistent trend was identified: over time, the MG demonstrated higher QoL scores across all SF-36 scales, indicating greater subjective clinical, social, and mental functioning in patients who underwent surgical correction using the authors' developed method of pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction.

Thus, although a certain degree of subjective similarity was observed between the two management strategies, the dynamics of overall condition and dysphagia according to the Visual Rating Scale (VRS), anxiety and depression according to the HADS, and state and trait anxiety according to the STAI suggest that, when choosing a technique for pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction, preference should be given to the method developed by the authors. This preference is based primarily on its greater economic efficiency, assuming comparable physical capacities of the patients. The use of this technique may reduce the physical, psychological, and social consequences of combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx,

esophagus, and stomach, accelerate the recovery of physical and mental health, and facilitate patients' social reintegration.

Conclusion. Formation of a pharyngeal anastomosis is inherently more technically demanding than the creation of an esophageal anastomosis. This is largely due to the anatomical characteristics of this region as well as the severity of cicatricial changes in the pharynx. Most surgeons involved in esophageal surgery, particularly in the management of post-burn cicatricial strictures, employ the same technique for pharyngeal anastomosis as for esophageal anastomosis. Although published results in the available literature demonstrate a tendency toward improvement, they remain far from optimal. The proposed variant of pharyngeal anastomosis is not a panacea for complications such as anastomotic leakage or the development of cicatricial strictures in the long-term period; however, it allowed a substantial reduction in their incidence.

Comparative intergroup analysis of the results of surgical correction of combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach according to the Visual Rating Scale (VRS) demonstrated greater subjective effectiveness of the method of forming a pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction developed by the authors compared with the standard surgical technique. According to the HADS depression subscale, normalization of patients' condition in the main group (MG) occurred after 6 months, whereas in the comparison group (CG) it was observed only after 2 years. Moreover, intergroup comparison revealed a statistically significant difference after 1 year of follow-up, indicating greater subjective psychological effectiveness of the authors' developed method of pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction compared with the formation of an anastomosis using an oblique-transverse incision of the esophagus.

We observed a statistically significant reduction in state anxiety according to the STAI test in the main group already at discharge, whereas in the comparison group this reduction was noted only 6 months after surgical correction. At the same time, trait anxiety according to the STAI test showed statistically significant changes compared with baseline as early as discharge in both groups; however, no statistically significant intergroup differences for this scale were detected throughout the entire follow-up period. Comparative intergroup analysis of the increase in the mean SF-36 score relative to baseline demonstrated a statistically significant difference in favor of the main group at 1 year after surgical correction ($p = 0.049336$). An identical pattern was observed at 2 years after surgery ($p = 0.039937$) and at 3 years of follow-up ($p = 0.049075$).

Nevertheless, a clear and persistent trend was identified: over time, the main group demonstrated higher quality-of-life scores across all SF-36 scales, indicating greater subjective clinical, social, and mental functioning in patients who underwent surgical correction using the authors' developed method of pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction. Based on the obtained quality-of-life results, it can be concluded that, although a certain degree of subjective similarity exists between the two management strategies, the dynamics of overall condition and dysphagia according to the Visual Rating Scale, anxiety and depression according to the HADS, and state and trait anxiety according to the STAI support the preference for the authors' developed method when selecting a technique for pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass esophageal reconstruction. This preference is largely justified by its greater economic efficiency, assuming comparable physical capacities of patients, and may contribute to reducing the physical, psychological, and social consequences of combined post-burn cicatricial strictures, accelerating recovery of physical and mental health, and enhancing patients' social reintegration.

Conclusion statement. The method of forming a pharyngocolonic anastomosis during bypass coloplasty implemented in clinical practice improved the effectiveness of surgical correction in patients with combined post-burn cicatricial strictures of the pharynx, esophagus, and stomach, reduced the recurrence rate of dysphagia, enhanced quality of life, and promoted patients' social rehabilitation.

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